

QUALICO 2025

Quantitative Linguistics Conference 2025, Brno, Czechia
June 26–28

International Quantitative Linguistics Association

MUNI
ARTS

Thursday 26 June		
8:30-9:30	Registration Hall (Building B)	
9:30-9:45	Official opening Room B 2.13	
9:45-10:30	Plenary lecture Gustav Herdan and mobile Quantitative Linguistics: Brno/Brünn – Vienna – Bristol <i>Emmerich Kelih</i> Room B 2.13	
	Room B 2.13 Chair: Jan Andres	Room B 2.23 Chair: Petra Mutlová
10:30-11:00	On a mathematical formulation of a theory of language <i>Ján Mačutek, Gejza Wimmer, Michaela Koščová</i>	Evaluating the Effectiveness of Different Topic Modeling Techniques on a Technical Corpus: A Comparative Study <i>Alessandro Meneghini, Arjuna Tuzzi</i>
11:00-11:30	Long-Range Dependence in Word Time Series <i>Paweł Wieczyński, Łukasz Dębowski</i>	Investigating Context Awareness in Automatic Pragmatic Annotation <i>Nándor Virág, Tibor Szécsényi</i>
11:30-12:00	No hard constraint on word order in the noun phrase. The science of the unseen <i>Ramon Ferrer-i-Cancho</i>	Automatic quantitative text analysis of contemporary French-language literatures from Europe, Africa and Canada <i>Ewa Kalinowska, Adam Pawtowski, Tomasz Walkowiak</i>
12:00-14:00	Lunch break	
	Room B 2.13 Chair: Haruko Sanada	Room B 2.23 Chair: George Mikros
14:00-14:30	A dynamical system approach to sign language <i>Jan Andres, Martina Benešová, Eva Fišerová, Jiří Langer</i>	Computational Thematics and Lexical Variation in Brazilian Novels: The Phenomenon of Regionalism <i>Adriana Pagano, André Coneglian, Maciej Eder</i>
14:30-15:00	Pseudosyllable in sign language <i>Jiří Langer, Jan Andres, Martina Benešová, Eva Fišerová</i>	How do translators deal with repeated reporting verbs in literary texts? A multifactorial comparative Study in English-to-Russian and English-to-Slovak language pair <i>Łukasz Grabowski, Daniel Borysowski, Filip Kalaš, Lorenzo Mastropiero</i>
15:00-15:30	Studying Borel normality of Spontaneous Japanese in binary expression <i>Yosuke Takubo, Masayuki Asahara, Makoto Yamazaki</i>	The BALAGHA Score: A Quantitative Linguistics Approach to Arabic Rhetorical Analysis <i>Mandar Marathe</i>
15:30-16:00	Coffee break	

	Room B 2.13 Chair: Herman Miosl	Room B 2.23 Chair: Martina Benešová
16:00-16:30	The distribution of dependency distance and hierarchical distance in contemporary written Japanese and its influencing factors <i>Linxuan Wang, Shuiyuan Yu</i>	The Wheel of Time: The Computational Stylometry Comparison of Robert Jordan and Brandon Sanderson <i>Nikolaos Maniotis, Athanassios Karassimos</i>
16:30-17:00	Confirming the Minimization Effect in MDD and MHD among Second Language Learners <i>Saeko Komori, Masatoshi Sugiura</i>	Stylometric Analysis of Dramas by the Čapek Brothers <i>Petr Pořízka</i>
17:00-18:00	Welcome drink Faculty courtyard / Hall (Building B)	
18:00-19:00	IQLA business meeting Room B 2.13	
Friday 27 June		
	Room B 2.13 Chair: Maud Reveilhac	
9:00-9:30	Random Forest Binary Classification for Word Origin Attribution based on Word Embeddings. A case study in Modern Hindi <i>Jacek Bąkowski</i>	
9:30-10:00	On Linguistic Complexity: Form-Meaning Pairing Through Subword Token Polysemy <i>Takuto Nakayama</i>	
10:00-10:30	Coffee break	
	Room B 2.13 Chair: Ramon Ferrer-i-Cancho	
10:30-11:00	Quantitative Linguistics and Large Language Models: Epistemological Challenges and Applications <i>Antoni Hernández-Fernández, Bernardino Casas, Jaume Baixeries Juvillà, Neus Català Roig</i>	
11:00-11:30	Comparison of Human-Written and LLM-Generated Texts: A Complete QL Package <i>Jiří Milička</i>	
11:30-12:00	AI as a Democratic Actor: Investigating LLM Narratives on Democracy <i>Maud Reveilhac</i>	
12:00-14:00	Lunch break	
	Room B 2.13 Chair: Sheila Embelton	
14:00-15:00	Plenary lecture Communicative efficiency: linguistic laws and orders <i>Natalia Levshina</i>	
15:00-15:30	Language universals in sentence length: Comparing sentence length distributions of 10 languages <i>Yikai Zhou, Haitao Liu</i>	
15:30-16:00	Recursive characteristics of the length and order of elements in Japanese by linguistic layer: Relationship between morpheme length and position within clause constituents <i>Haruko Sanada</i>	
16:00-16:30	Coffee break	

16:30-17:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Poster session Hall (Building B)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Rolling topics in Positivist and Young Poland novels: a comparative study <i>Wojciech Łukasik</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Corpus-driven threshold-based argument categorization and word-sense disambiguation on verbal semantic selection for subjects <i>Nándor Virág</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Comparative Analysis of Thesauri for Functional Expression Classification Using Machine Learning <i>Bocheng Chen</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">LexaMorf: A Tool for Lexico-Morphological Quantitative Text Analysis <i>Petr Pořízka</i></p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Room B 2.13 Chair: Adriana Pagano</p>
17:00-17:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Distance-Based Relevance Zones: A Case Study from Norwegian Digitized Collections <i>Lars Johnsen</i></p>
17:30-18:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Neural Implementation of lexical meaning using topographic representation of environmental input topology <i>Hermann Moisl</i></p>
18:00-18:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Government proposals for 2022 Elections in Brazil: Topic Modelling and Political Spectrum <i>Rodrigo de Lima Lopes</i></p>
18:45-20:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Guided tour of the gardens of Brno's villas Starts at faculty courtyard</p>
20:00-00:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Conference dinner Restaurant "Na Chatě", Černopolní 54, Brno https://maps.app.goo.gl/AyF4DC2oY9ZFKWL69</p>
Saturday 28 June	
	<p style="text-align: center;">Room B 2.13 Chair: Adam Pawłowski</p>
9:00-10:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Plenary lecture Language models as cognitively realistic mathematical models of grammar <i>Andrea Nini</i></p>
10:00-10:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Investigating the Impact of Semantic Similarity on Stylometric Attribution Using Controlled Artificial Texts and Delta Distances <i>George Mikros, Radek Čech, Petra Mutlová</i></p>
10:30-11:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Coffee break</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Room B 2.13 Chair: Emmerich Kelih</p>
11:00-11:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Dimensionality Reduction Methods for Authorship Attribution <i>Antonio Calcagni, Livio Finos, Andrea Sciandra, Arjuna Tuzzi</i></p>
11:30-12:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Stylometric Analysis for Machine Translation Evaluation: Investigating Delta Distance as a Measure of Stylistic Fidelity <i>George Mikros, Vilemini Sisoni, Vasilis Manousakis, Kelly Polychroniou</i></p>

12:00-12:30	Distribution and Frequency of Words in Texts: An Analysis of Occurrence Intervals and Positions <i>Makoto Yamazaki</i>
12:30-14:30	Lunch break
	Room B 2.13 Chair: Jiří Milička
14:30-15:00	Menzerath's law: Non-replicable significant inverse relationship between number of phonemes per word and phoneme inventory size <i>Gertraud Fenk-Oczlon</i>
15:00-15:30	Does Menzerath-Altmann Law hold true for English-as-a-foreign-language learner English? <i>Mengge Wang, Jingyang Jiang</i>
15:30-16:00	The Menzerath-Altmann law: Good news and bad news <i>Ján Mačutek, Radek Čech, Michaela Nogolová</i>
16:00-16:30	Closing session B 2.13